

g/litre did not control *L. natalensis*. Metaldehyde inefficiency at the highest concentration and efficiency at lower concentrations may have been due to a protective mechanism developed by

Limnea. B. aegyptiaca nut and leaf powder controlled *L. natalensis*, but concentrations higher than 0.75 g leaf powder/litre harmed azolla. *D. heudelotianum* affected neither

Limnea nor azolla. Treating azolla multiplication plots with 0.25 g *D. heudelotianum* bark powder or *B. aegyptiaca* leaf powder provides an effective, inexpensive control. *ℒ*

Nitrogen use efficiency in rice

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We evaluated urea split, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), neem-coated urea (NCU), lac-coated urea (LCU), gypsum-coated urea (GCU), urea supergranules (USG), and urea coal acid (UCA) with 0, 40, 80, and 120 kg N/ha for rice at Varanasi. The experiment was in a split-plot design with N sources in main plots and levels in subplots.

Four doses of the coated fertilizers and USG were applied 1 wk after transplanting Jaya. Half of urea split was basal and half in equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation. PK at 22-42 kg/ha were applied at transplanting. Fields were flooded with 5±2 cm water throughout the study.

USG performed best, followed by SCU and NCU (see table). Each N increment significantly increased grain yield. *ℒ*

Effect of N sources and levels on rice grain yield, Varanasi, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1982	1983
N sources		
Urea split	3.1	3.0
SCU	3.5	3.2
NCU	3.2	3.2
LCU	2.8	3.1
GCU	3.2	3.0
USG	3.5	3.2
UCA	2.5	3.0
S. Em ±	0.1	0.08
LSD 5%	0.4	0.2
N levels (kg/ha)		
0	2.2	1.9
40	3.0	2.8
80	3.4	3.6
120	3.9	4.1
S. Em ±	0.1	0.06
LSD 5%	0.4	0.2

Effect of sowing time on yield of rice varieties in two locations in Cuba

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Even slight changes in sowing time will substantially change yield and duration of rice varieties. In 1977-80 we recorded the effect of year-around sowing on modern rices.

Varietal response and interaction between variety and sowing date was highly significant in all 36 sowings. Dry season (Nov-Mar) grain yield averaged

1.5 t/ha more than that in wet season (Apr-Oct), independent of variety.

Medium-duration IR880-C9, Caribe-1, and IR1529 performed best when planted from December to August (see figure), depending upon location. Short-duration P723 yielded better when planted from late December to March, and from April to early August. Photoperiod-sensitive Caribe-7 should be planted from April to June.

Because of low temperature during reproductive stage, September to November sowings generally yielded lowest. *ℒ*

Favorable sowing range for 5 rices in Cuba.

Seasonal variation in azolla biomass production in Jorhat

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Azolla pinnata grows naturally in low-lying fields, shallow ditches, and channels in Assam. In 1981-82 we

studied azolla biomass production with different levels of inoculants and nutrients (see table) in 4-m² dugout plots lined with 750 gauge black polythene. The experiment had three replications.

Seasonal azolla growth varied significantly. Azolla biomass production increased from Mar to Jun, declined in

Azolla biomass production, Jorhat, India, 1981-82.

Treatments ^a	Azolla biomass (t/ha)												Mean
	1981						1982						
	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	
L ₀ P ₀ I ₁	23.8	6.8	21.0	19.3	14.0	18.5	6.3	18.4	17.5	19.4	21.2	26.5	17.7
L ₀ P ₀ I ₂	28.5	6.7	26.0	22.2	17.4	20.0	8.8	15.0	17.0	18.4	24.0	26.4	19.2
L ₀ P ₁ I ₁	30.3	14.2	27.5	20.8	17.5	25.3	13.5	21.9	25.3	20.2	26.0	29.6	22.7
L ₀ P ₂ I ₁	34.6	14.0	31.0	26.1	23.7	21.3	11.0	21.0	26.4	24.7	22.2	30.3	23.8
L ₀ P ₁ I ₂	29.5	14.7	30.0	25.5	26.6	26.9	15.7	22.5	25.1	20.9	27.1	32.4	24.7
L ₀ P ₂ I ₂	31.9	13.7	32.4	27.7	25.3	30.4	16.3	17.0	19.5	25.0	24.6	34.9	24.9
L ₁ P ₀ I ₁	16.0	4.1	26.0	17.3	12.9	15.4	11.3	12.9	18.6	20.5	23.7	30.8	17.4
L ₁ P ₀ I ₂	28.3	5.6	25.8	20.9	18.0	26.5	18.5	17.0	20.3	19.3	24.4	18.6	20.3
L ₁ P ₁ I ₁	30.0	16.9	31.2	35.2	24.7	28.4	19.2	21.9	20.8	28.1	27.9	35.1	26.6
L ₁ P ₂ I ₁	35.3	12.5	30.4	32.0	27.6	29.2	17.4	25.1	27.2	25.4	29.2	39.3	27.7
L ₁ P ₁ I ₂	31.3	15.9	28.8	30.1	30.1	26.0	19.6	23.0	22.9	24.8	29.9	28.4	25.9
L ₁ P ₂ I ₂	33.7	16.0	33.8	31.0	26.4	30.1	18.4	26.3	26.1	20.5	30.0	34.1	27.2
Mean	29.4	11.7	28.7	25.7	22.0	24.8	14.7	20.2	22.2	22.4	25.8	30.6	
	<i>Mean av water temp (°C)</i>												
	29	38	32	31	26	24	22	25	28	30	30	30	

Season (mo) CD (0.05) 2.768
 Lime (L) 1.151
 Phosphate (P) 1.384
 CV = 14.77%

^a L₀ = no lime, L₁ = 1 t lime/ha, P₀ = no P, P₁ = 9 kg P/ha, P₂ = 18 kg P/ha, I₁ = 0.5 t inoculum/ha, I₂ = 1 t inoculum/ha.

Jul, and was lowest in Aug. Production increased in Sep and then remained stable until Dec (see table). Variations in production were related to weather, particularly temperature. In Aug, when production was lowest, water temperature reached 44° C and averaged 38°C.

Production also varied with nutrient management. Applying 1 t lime and 18 kg P/ha significantly increased production over no-lime and no-P treatments (see table). P affected production more than lime did. Inoculum amount did not affect biomass production. *ℒ*

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Effect of salinity on *Azolla pinnata*

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We studied the effect of salinity on *A. pinnata*, Coimbatore strain, with a soil extract solution with 20 ppm superphosphate as base medium. Sodium chloride was applied at 0.01,

0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09, 0.1, and 0.2%. *A. pinnata* was inoculated at 5 g per plastic container and fresh weight was recorded after 14 d. In another experiment, 500 ppm neem *Azadirachta indica* cake was added to the medium.

A. pinnata yield decreased as salinity increased (see table), but neem cake reduced the detrimental effect of salinity. *ℒ*

Effect of salinity on *A. pinnata*, Tamil Nadu, India.

Sodium chloride (%)	Biomass (g/tub)	% decrease over control	Biomass (g/tub) with neem cake amendment (500 ppm)	% increase or decrease over control
Control without superphosphate	5.3	-	5.4	-
Neem cake alone	NT ^a	-	8.8	+62
0.01	5.2	3	8.5	+57
0.02	5.0	6	7.5	+38
0.03	4.7	11	7.0	+30
0.04	4.7	11	6.7	+24
0.05	4.6	13	5.4	+ 0
0.06	4.4	18	5.2	- 3
0.07	4.3	20	5.2	- 3
0.08	4.0	25	5.2	- 3
0.09	4.0	25	4.8	-11
0.10	3.7	31	4.7	-13
0.20	3.6	32	4.0	-26
SE	0.006		0.577	
CD	0.017		1.678	

^aNot tested.

Rice response to and residual effect of Zn application in a sandy lowland soil

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In 1981 wet season and 1981-82 dry season, we studied IR880 rice response to and residual effect of Zn application in a sandy soil with 1.77 ppm available Zn and pH 7.1. Zn at 0, 2.8, 5.8, 8.5, and 11.5 kg/ha was applied before seeding.

In wet season, plots were in a randomized complete block design with eight replications. To study residual effect in dry season, Zn was applied to four of the same plots and the remaining four received no Zn.

In wet season, all treatments were significantly better than no-Zn control. Rice yield increased from 3.4 to 4.5 t/ha (see figure). In dry season, rice yield increased from 3.5 to 5.0 t/ha (see figure), and best results were obtained with 8.5 and 11.5 kg Zn/ha.

Zn application had a substantial residual effect (see table). Although